

Digital Currency and Transactions at Glance

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Abstract:

With the advent of cryptocurrencies like bitcoin, pie; transactions saw new era, in terms of investment. In this paper, we shall attempt to discuss about new means of digital currency, for flexible transactions, along with discussion for cryptoness in currencies.

Introduction:

In our title, we have used word, "currency", which throughout the paper would mean currencies, and coins too. We shall begin our discussion from common machines that does tellering of money, like as ATM. An ATM machine can recognize currencies as per their varying values, while we do withdraw money from ATM. Another machine, used in tellering service is machine, that counts total number of currencies, which are seen in banks too.

We shall begin our theory, by proposing an app, like as of mobile wallets, that can do, transactions among inter-financial institutions. An app like as ATM, that can recognize, not only money, but even can provide us currency numbers, among wide range of currencies, while doing transactions.

Each nations do have their own central banks, as well as monetary policies, thus recognizing money, remains to them; where as in our proposed theory, on discussing about Nepal, and central Bank of Nepal, i.e. Nepal Rastra Bank, a mobile wallet type of app, that can keep records of our currencies with currency number, by which we do financial transactions is what our theory sought. Same can be applied for coins, by means of recognizing coins.

When foreign transactions are talked, then the app must be able to recognize currencies across the world, whenever we would do transactions and through such an app, we can study, how many, any currency got transacted, deposited and withdrawn.

Obviously it is not a non-paper based currency, and our currencies would be safe at Banks and vaults, where as we can know, which currency got transacted, and how many times it got transacted.

When cryptography is studied, then by means of an app, encryption can be added, firewalls can be added, and our digital signatures too can be added, which would mean, even a lost money can be traced to find owner of currency, based on currency number, digital signatures and transactions from app.

Conclusion:

Our proposed app, seems to be an ATM in an app, as a form of mobile wallet, but performs greater than that of mobile wallet, by means of recognizing currencies and coins, as per their unique identification number, among each other.

Pros and Cons:

Since the app is intended to provide details, of currencies across the world, Forex transactions would be initial problem, when talked for Nepal, and that would depend upon central bank of any nation, to formulate monetary policies, so that, app can do forex transactions across the world, based on value of currency. Author does doubt, if all central banks would allow recognition of their currencies and coins or not, but when is allowed in an app, then that would be a terrific pros.

Similar another advantage is, our app would reduce the cost to produce currencies and coins, as each central banks need to follow rules for printing of currencies, like as deposit of foreign currency, deposit of gold e.t.c, and that means, currencies once printed would be sufficient to do transactions, if we can keep our paper based currencies and coins in safe vault. Keeping currency safe is just to ensure that, there exists currency, which can be shown whenever necessary, during financial transactions, if digital medium isn't sought . Similarly record keeping of currencies can be achieved and flow of currencies and coins during financial transactions. If the app is provided with currency scanner, then peoples can keep currencies in their own homes and do financial transactions via the app.

More-or-less, our app, would allow us to study Economics, based on transaction of money, and would allow us to answer the question, "How many times did any currency got transacted before it was teared, or new currency was printed?"

Actknowledgement:

Author being a lazy fellow, had submitted letters to banks, including Nepal Rastra Bank, for various monetary topics, and hasn't received response, thus thought to actknowldge the application letters sent to various banks.